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Enhanced internalization of magnetic nanoparticles in cancer cell lines

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ABSTRACT

The biocompatibility of three dextran-coated iron oxide nanoparticles was tested in two human tumor cell lines (HeLa and A-549). Cationic magnetic nanoparticles have important advantages in relation to the intracellular localization of the nanoparticles, detection of particles inside cells for relatively long periods of time and the absolute lack of cytotoxicity. On the contrary, neutral particles showed no uptake into cells and negative particles showed uptake only at high doses together with some cell damage.

KEYWORDS: Magnetic nanoparticles, HeLa cells, A-549 cells, surface charge, cytotoxicity, microtubules.

Magnetic nanoparticles are attracting much attention because of their medical applications, as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), as heating mediators for cancer therapy (hyperthermia) and as drug delivery devices.^{1,2} A way of improving the efficiency of some of these techniques is the cell labelling with magnetic nanoparticles, which is not an easy task when working with non phagocyte cells. On the other hand, recent publications advice of the risk that some nanomaterials suppose for the human health if they have not been carefully evaluated.^{3,4} The evaluation of the possible toxic effects that nanomaterials can induce in the human organism has become a question of vital importance.

A wide variety of iron oxide nanoparticles with different coatings (polyethyleneglycol, dextran, chitosan, etc.) to stabilize and to improve the nanoparticle's bioeffects, have been analyzed in different cell cultures. Macrophage cell lines are currently used for diagnosis magnetic resonance imaging studies,⁵ while cancer cell lines are usually chosen for intracellular magnetic hyperthermia and/or drug delivery.⁶ It has been reported that anionic iron oxide nanoparticles provide a highly efficient label for a wide range of cell types.⁷⁻⁹ However, there is very little information in the literature concerning the interaction of cells with cationic iron oxide nanoparticles.¹⁰ In this sense the precise influence of the surface charge of iron oxide nanoparticles on cellular internalization remains to be elucidated. Thus, the aim of this work is to synthesize dextran-Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with similar particle and aggregate size, but different surface charge (neutral, cationic, and anionic) and to carry out a comparative study of their biological effects on two human tumor cell lines (HeLa and A-549). The nanoparticles-cell interactions were assessed by analysis of the efficiency cell internalization, cytotoxicity and changes in microtubules organization, after nanoparticles incubation.

Coprecipitation method was used for the synthesis of the magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles and they were coated with three molecules, based on glucose structure, to stabilize the particles in aqueous suspension under physiological conditions (pH and salinity). Coating confers not only steric repulsion but also different surface charge. Thus, neutral, positive and negative iron oxide nanoparticles were obtained by coating with dextran (sample D), aminodextran (sample DX) and heparin (sample DH), respectively. Samples were subjected to centrifugation and filtration process to reduce the hydrodynamic size below 200 nm. The hydrodynamic size is the aggregate size of the particles in solution and should be below 200 nm to fit one of the requirements for intravenous injection and therefore *in vivo* biomedical applications.^{11,12}

A typical transmission electron microscopy image of the nanoparticles generated by coprecipitation is shown in **Figure 1** together with the particle size distribution. Mean particle size ranged from 6 to 10 nm depending on the coating process and the size deviation around 20%. Smaller sizes were obtained when the coprecipitation was carried out in the presence of the polymer. That is the case of nanoparticles coated with dextran and aminodextran (samples D and DX). However, when the polymer was added after the nanoparticle formation, bigger particles up to 10 nm in size were obtained and this is the case of the heparin coated sample (Sample DH). It should be noted that sample D is similar to commercial contrast agents such as Feridex.^{13,14}

Fig. 1.

Nanoparticles were identified as magnetite by X-ray diffraction (supporting information) and no rest of other iron oxide phases was found. Crystal size calculated from the broadening of (311) reflection peak was close to the mean particle size obtained from TEM images. Infrared spectroscopy spectra for the coated particles presented new bands at frequencies between 1000 and 1400 cm^{-1} , associated to the presence of the polymers (**Figure 2**). Magnetic behavior of the powders at room temperature was reversible for all the samples as expected for particles of around 10 nm in size¹⁵ and therefore the particles are superparamagnetic, fitting one of the requirements for biomedical applications.^{11,16} Moreover, magnetization curves at room temperature do not change substantially with the coating (**Figure 3**), which means that the nature and the strength of the bond between the different coatings and the magnetic nanoparticles is similar.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

To investigate the surface properties of the nanoparticles, zeta-potential measurements at different pH were taken for the three colloidal suspensions as shown in **Figure 4**. It can be observed that at pH 7, the surface charge varied from +26 mV for the amino-dextran coated sample (DX) to -9 mV for the dextran coated (sample D) one and -27 mV for the heparin coated sample (DH). The difference in charge is expected to affect the ability of the particles to enter the cell and in general the interaction between particles and cells.

Fig. 4

In this work cells cultured in standard conditions were incubated at variable concentrations (0.05, 0.1 and 0.5 mg Fe/mL culture medium) of nanoparticles at different times (1-24 h). After incubation, cells were washed three times with PBS and processed in different ways immediately, 24 or 48 h later.

Firstly, cells were observed under the bright-light microscope without being processed. Under these conditions, sample D was not located inside HeLa or A-549 cells under any condition. However, the cationic sample DX was detected inside the cells under all experimental conditions. The evolution with time of the DX nanoparticle-cell interaction was as follows. First, nanoparticles aggregate outside the cell membrane (Figure 5A), and then are uptaken homogeneously into the cells (Figure 5B), forming big lumps in the cytoplasm but always outside the cell nucleus. The intracellular pattern distribution for sample DX was like brown cytoplasmic spots of different sizes, which corresponds with endosomes, in both cell types (Figure 5B-G). A similar subcellular distribution has been described for other nanoparticles in other cellular types, and seems to be due to endocytosis (the mechanism for which nanoparticles enter into the cells).^{7,17} Besides, it was observed that internalized DX nanoparticles, were split between the daughter cells in each cell division cycle (Figure 5G). Moreover, DX stayed inside the cells during long periods of times, allowing their microscopically visualization 48h after removing sample DX from cell culture medium.

Fig. 5

Control and DX treated cells growing on coverslips were also fixed in cold methanol, followed by toluidine blue stained, that allows preserving the samples to analyze possible alterations in cell morphology. Nanoparticles were observed inside both cell lines, with an identical distribution pattern than in living cells (Figure 5H-I). The nuclear and cell morphology were similar to those of the control cells in all experimental conditions (Figure 5J). On the contrary, the anionic sample (DH) was detected inside the cells for both cell culture lines only when used a 0.5 mg Fe/mL culture medium concentration after 24h of incubation (Figure 5K,L). However the intracellular amount of DH was clearly less than the amount of DX observed in both cell lines. From these results it is clear that internalization of nanoparticles inside both cell types depended on concentration, incubation time and nanoparticle coating charge. It is important to note that, despite other nanoparticles for which it is necessary the use of complementary techniques (Perls' Prussian blue staining, TEM or fluorescent-labelled nanoparticles) for their visualization,^{5,7,9,17,18} our DX nanoparticles do not require the use of such techniques.

Fig. 6

Cell survival was evaluated by means of the standard MTT assay (Figure 6A, B). Only sample DH at the highest concentration (0.5 mg Fe/mL) affected significantly the cell viability (~25%), both in HeLa as well as in A-549.

On the other hand, the possible alterations induced by the nanoparticles in the cytoskeletal components were also evaluated. Microtubules (MTs), are highly dynamic cytoskeletal fibers with critical functions in eukaryotic cells such as intracellular transport,

organization of intracellular structure, and cell division. Indirect immunofluorescence analysis to α -tubulin (DNA counterstained with Hoechst 33258) in HeLa and A-549 cells, incubated with D

Fig. 7

and DX, showed that the percentage of cells in mitosis (mitotic index, MI), was similar in HeLa and A-549 to the control ($4.9 \pm 0.1\%$ and $4.8 \pm 0.2\%$, respectively) under all the experimental

conditions. More important, in both cell lines the large amount of DX nanoparticles inside the cells did not alter the normal morphology and distribution of interphase microtubules. In the same way, mitotic spindles and chromosomes distribution were also similar to the metaphase of the control cells (Figure 7A-F).

However, the results obtained for sample DH differed according to the cell line used. In HeLa cells, 24 h after the incubation with DH 0.5 mg Fe/mL a two-fold increase in MI was detected ($8.5 \pm 0.2 \%$), due a higher number of cells in metaphase and most of these metaphases ($93.1 \pm 0.1 \%$) were aberrant. The most frequent modifications were the presence of extra poles in mitotic spindles (multipolar metaphases) and misaligned chromosomes (Figure 7G-H). On the contrary, interphasic MTs did not show any alteration with regard to the control (Figure 7I). Several reports have described that drugs with antiproliferative effects through perturbation of microtubule dynamics and mitotic spindle formation, induce a metaphase arrest of cell cycle and subsequently cell death by apoptosis.^{19,20} This could be associated with the $\sim 25\%$ decrease in HeLa cells viability detected by MTT assay. It is interesting to note that, to our knowledge, this is the first time that a metaphase arrest induced by any type of nanoparticle is described. Likewise, only few studies have examined the effect of nanoparticles, iron oxide included, on microtubules. Dextran-coated iron nanoparticles internalized into human dermal fibroblasts, induce several alterations in tubulin and other cytoskeletal proteins.²¹ However, gold nanoparticles have been described that not interfered with cytoskeletal organisation (F-actin and β -tubulin) in an immortalized primary human fibroblasts cell line.²²

A-549 cells incubated with 0.5 mg Fe/mL, 24h DH, showed that mitotic spindles, chromosome distribution and interphase MTs were not altered (Figure 7J), as opposed to HeLa cells. However, the MI evaluated immediately after treatment was significantly lower than in control cells ($0.97 \pm 0.1 \%$ vs $4.8 \pm 0.2 \%$). After 24h the mitotic index recovered to values closer to that of untreated cells ($3.8 \pm 0.1 \%$).

In conclusion, our results indicate that cell response is dependent on the surface charge of the nanoparticles surface and cationic dextran have excellent properties for possible biomedical applications (drug delivery, hyperthermia cancer therapy, magnetic resonance imaging), since they provide efficient cell labeling for relative long periods, can be easily detected by optical microscopy and do not alter the cell viability or the cell cycle. Besides, those with a negatively charged cover are potentially toxic and ferromagnetic nanoparticles with an uncharged cover are not internalized inside of cancer cells (without phagocyte capacity).

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Transmission electron microscopy images of the iron oxide nanoparticles prepared by coprecipitation.

Figure 2. Infrared spectroscopy spectra for coated iron oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 3. Magnetization curve at room temperature for coated iron oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 4. Zeta-potential measurements at different pH for colloidal suspensions prepared from coated iron oxide nanoparticles.

Figure 5. Photomicrographs of HeLa and A-549 cells incubated with DX or DH and visualized by optical microscopy (bright-field). (A) HeLa cells incubated for 1 h with 0.1 mg Fe/mL DX. (B, C) Nanoparticles internalized inside living HeLa cells, after 24 h incubation with DX 0.1 mg Fe/mL. (D) HeLa cells incubated 24 h with DX 0.5 mg Fe/mL. (E, F) DX retained into A-549 cells incubated 24 h with 0.1 and 0.5 mg Fe/mL DX, respectively. (G) HeLa cells incubated with 0.1 mg Fe/mL DX after cell division. (H) DX within HeLa cells incubated 24 h with 0.1 mg Fe/mL DX, post-incubated 24 h in free culture medium and stained with toluidine blue. (I) DX internalized into A-549 cells incubated for 24 h with 0.5 mg Fe/mL. (J) Morphology of untreated (control) HeLa cell, after toluidine blue staining. (K) HeLa cells incubated 24 h with 0.5 mg Fe/mL DH. (L) A-549 cells incubated 24 h with 0.5 mg Fe/mL DH and toluidine blue stained. Scale bars = 5 μ m.

Figure 6. Cell survival evaluated by means of the standard MTT assay. (A) HeLa cells. (B) A-549 cells.

Figure 7. HeLa and A-549 cells incubated for 24 h with 0.5 mg Fe/mL DX or DH, stained with tubulin-specific antibodies and DNA counterstaining with Hoechst 33258. Fluorescence photomicrographs are merged images of microtubules (green) and DNA (blue). (A) HeLa cell at interphase preincubated with DX. (B) The same A cell observed by bright-field microscopy. (C, D) Metaphase A-549 cell treated with DX and observed by fluorescence and bright-field microscopy, respectively. (E, F) Interphase and metaphase HeLa and A-549 control cells, respectively. (G, H) Details of the abnormalities of metaphases induced by DH in HeLa cells. (I) Interphase HeLa cells incubated with DH. (J) Interphase and metaphase A-549 cell treated with DX. Bars: 5 μ m.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

1. Synthesis of nanoparticles and characterisation

Magnetite nanoparticles were synthesized by the coprecipitation method. A mixture of 10.01 g of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M_w=278.02$ g/mol) and 8.08 g of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M_w=404$ g/mol) was dissolved in 50 mL of water previously bubbled with nitrogen to eliminate oxygen to keep the $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio in 1:1.8. The iron salt solution was slowly added to a deoxygenated 400 mL basic solution of NaOH (pH 12) magnetically stirred and kept for 5 hours under a nitrogen flow. The precipitate was then centrifuged at 9000 to eliminate impurities and large aggregates.

Samples D and DX consisted on magnetite nanoparticles coated with dextran and amino dextran, in particular DEAE-dextran, respectively. The coating was incorporated into the Na(OH) solution (4.32 g of $M_w=10000$ g/mol) before the iron salt addition.

Sample DH consisted of magnetite nanoparticles coated by heparin after the particle synthesis. First of all, 100 mg of magnetite nanoparticles were dispersed by sonication in water at pH 5 and then 38.5 mg of heparin sodium salt were added to the dispersion. The dispersion was sonicated for 15 minutes and centrifuged to eliminate the excess of heparin that is unbound to the magnetite nanoparticles surface.

Particle size and size distribution were studied by transmission electron microscopy using a 200-keV JEOL-2000 FXII microscope. TEM samples were prepared by placing one drop of a dilute suspension of magnetite nanoparticles in water on a carbon coated copper grid and allowing the solvent to evaporate at room temperature. The average particle size (D_{TEM}) and distribution were evaluated by measuring the largest internal dimension of 300 particles.

Hydrodynamic size and evolution of the zeta potential versus the pH was evaluated in a ZETASIZER NANO-ZS device (Malvern Instruments). Hydrodynamic size was measured from a dilute suspension of the sample in water in a plastic cuvette at pH 7. Zeta potential was also measured from a dilute suspension of the sample in water in a special Zeta potential cuvette with 0.01 M concentration of KNO_3 at different pH.

The iron oxide phase of the particles was identified by powder X-ray diffraction. The patterns were collected between 5-80 (2θ) degrees in a Philips 1710 diffractometer using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation. The crystal size (D_{XRD}) was calculated from the broadening of the (311) reflection of the spinel structure following standard procedures.

Fourier transform infrared spectra of the iron oxide nanoparticles were recorded between 3600 and 400 cm^{-1} in a Nicolet 20 SXC FTIR in order to confirm the phase of the iron oxide, the nature of the coating and its bonding to the surface. Samples were prepared by diluting the iron oxide powder in KBr at 2% by weight and pressing into a pellet.

Magnetic characterization of the samples was carried out in a vibrating sample magnetometer (MLVSM9 MagLab 9 T, Oxford Instrument) at room temperature. Magnetization curves were recorded by first saturating the sample in a field of 3 T and then sweeping the field range between 3 and -3 T at 0.5 T/min. Saturation magnetization (M_s), and the coercive field (H_c) were determined for each sample. The M_s values were evaluated by extrapolating to infinite field the experimental results obtained in the high field range where magnetization linearly increases with $1/H$.

2. Cell cultures, internalization, toluidine blue staining and evaluation of cell viability

Two human tumor cell lines, HeLa (cervical carcinoma) and A-549 (lung carcinoma), were grown as monolayers in Dulbecco's modified Eagles's medium (DMEM) with 50 units/mL penicillin, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin and supplemented with foetal bovine serum (FBS), at a final concentration of 10%. All the media, sera and antibiotics were provided by Gibco (Paisley, UK). Cell cultures were performed in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere at 37 °C and maintained in an incubator. For the experiment the cells were seeded into 24 multiwell plates at an initial density of 3,500 cells/well. Treatments were initiated three days after plating (approximately 70% confluence). Depending on the experiments, the cells were seeded on 10-mm square glass coverslips placed into the wells.

In order to analyze the internalization of nanoparticles, HeLa and A-549 cells were grown on coverslips and incubated for 1-24 h with different NP concentrations (0.05, 0.1 and 0.5 mg Fe/mL culture medium). After incubation the -containing medium was removed, the cells were washed three times with PBS and observed immediately under bright light microscopy. DX release was analyzed after several periods of post-incubation (24-48 h) in free culture medium. The cells were visualized directly or by toluidine blue staining.

After fixing them in ice-cold methanol (5 min), cells were stained with toluidine blue (0.05 mg/mL distilled water, 30 s), washed with distilled water and air dried. Preparations were mounted in DPX and observed under bright field microscopy. Microscopic observations and photographs were performed in an Olympus BX61, bright light and epifluorescence microscope, equipped with the ultraviolet and blue filter sets for fluorescence microscopy and

an Olympus DP50 digital camera. Photographs were processed using Adobe Photoshop CS software.

The viability of both, HeLa and A-549 cells was determined using MTT assay (Sigma, St. Louis, USA). Briefly, 24 h after incubation with nanoparticles, MTT was added to each well (100 µg/mL in medium) for 3 h at 37 °C. The formazan formed into the cells was dissolved adding 0.5 mL of DMSO in each dish, and the optical density was evaluated at 540 nm in a microplate reader (Tecan Spectra Fluor spectrophotometer). Cell survival was expressed as the percentage of absorption of treated cells in comparison with that of control cells (not incubated with any NP). The results obtained are the mean value and standard deviation (SD) from at least six experiments.

3. Immunofluorescence staining of α -tubulin

HeLa and A-549 cells grown on coverslips were treated with nanoparticles (0.5 mg Fe/mL) for 24 h and then immunostained for α -tubulin. Briefly, cells seeded upon coverslips were fixed in ice-cold methanol for 5 min, washed three times for 5 min with PBS, permeabilized 5 min with 0.5 % Triton X-100 (Sigma) in PBS, and later incubated with the primary monoclonal mouse anti- α -tubulin antibody (1:100 in PBS/BSA, Sigma) for 1h at 37 °C in a humidified chamber. The cells were washed with PBS three times during 5 min, and incubated with the secondary goat anti-mouse antibody fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-labelled (Sigma) at a dilution 1:50 for 1 h at 37 °C. Finally, the cells were washed three times with PBS, and counterstained with the fluorochrome to DNA, Hoechst 33258 (0.05 mg/mL in distilled water, 3 min), washed with distilled water and mounted in ProLong Gold antifade reagent (Molecular Probes, Eugene, USA). The fluorescence of FITC (green) and Hoechst 33258 (blue) was observed under a fluorescence microscope. The mitotic index (MI) was evaluated in immunofluorescence processed samples (control and treated). 4,000 cells were counted for each experimental point of at least three different experiments.